

Collapse of the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba On the 24th of June 1987 Anurādhapura, Sri Lanka

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More than two thousand years ago – during the second and first centuries BC – the first monumental *stūpas* locally known as *dāgābas* were built in Sri Lanka. Such dome-shaped monuments were containing relics of the historical Buddha or of Buddhist saints. And like all man-made structures, these *dāgābas* built of brick needed to be conserved and restored in regular intervals. In times of neglect the large *dāgābas* started to crumble and were overgrown by tropical vegetation. The roots of trees would penetrate the layers of brick and cause cracks thus further increasing damage. According to the *Mahāvamsa*, the Mirisavetiya (Maricavaṭṭī) Dāgāba was built on the spot where the *kunta* (royal standard) of Duṭṭhagāmaṇī (c. BC 161–137) had been stuck in the earth and could not be removed. (*Mhv.* 26.11–19). Duṭṭhagāmaṇī built a large *dāgāba* despite the warnings recorded in the *Mahāvamsa*: “*If our king shall begin to build so great a thupa, death will come upon him ere the thupa be finished; moreover, so great a thupa will be hard to repair*”. (*Mhv.* 29.52–53). The oldest reference to restoration works about two hundred fifty years after the initial construction of the Mirisavetiya refers to Gajabāhu I (c. 114–136 AD) who is credited with the making of a mantling for the *dāgāba*. About one hundred years later the *chattrāvalī* was restored by Vohārikatissa (c. 209–231 AD). Kassapa V (914–923 AD) restored the *dāgāba* and the *vihāra*.¹ During the 11th century the Mirisavetiya and all other *stūpas* and monasteries were ransacked by Cholas from South India. Among numerous other renovation projects, Parākramabāhu I (1153–1186 AD) enlarged the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba to a height of about 36.5 metres. Restorations were resumed again by Niśsaṅkamalla (1187–1196 AD).² For the next seven hundred years, the *dāgābas* and Buddhist monasteries of Anurādhapura lay mostly in ruins. It seems reasonable to assume that by the beginning of the 19th century, almost all formerly once intact ancient *dāgābas* and temples had fallen into a state of partial or total disrepair due to a variety of factors, such as lack of maintenance and defective building materials. Another obstacle was the fact that relics that are enshrined in *Stūpas* are desirable objects and as such were regularly targets of thieves. The Mirisavetiya Dāgāba shared same fate of being totally overgrown with all relics gone. (**Plates 1–2**).

¹ Wickremasinghe, D. M. de Z. 1912. *Epigraphia Zeylanica*, Vol. I: 51.

² Nicholas, C. W. 1959. “Historical Topography of Ancient and Medieval Ceylon,” *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society (Ceylon Branch) New Series*, Vol. VI: 136.

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No. 144.—ANURADHAPURA.—The Mirisaveti Dāgāba. Built by King Dutugemunu about the middle of the second century B.C.

1. Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura in 1870–1871. (Photo: Joseph Lawton).

2. Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura in the 1880s. (Photo: Skeen & Co 1880–1890s).

Renovations of the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba

As already mentioned above, *dāgābas* need to be restored in regular intervals. Henry Parker visited Anurādhapura for the first time in 1873 and recorded that the Mirisavetiya was little more than a conical mound covered with large trees and bushes, all the upper part having slipped down in a talus round its base (**Plates 1–2**). Anurādhapura's first government agent J. F. Dixon, with the help of James G. Smither, first cleared the area surrounding the *dāgāba*. Excavations of the Mirisavetiya were resumed in 1883 and the ruins of two image houses on the northern and southern sides of the *dāgāba* were discovered. In 1888 the first attempt of renovation began using prison labour under the direction of the public works department utilising a grant from the King of Siam, but the work could not be completed. According to H. C. P. Bell, the Archaeological Commissioner, by 1890 the ground around the Mirisavetiya had been cleared for a considerable time, and all ruins that existed above the surface were known. Bell added that a description of the Mirisavetiya entourage would not be possible at present.³ Sixteen years later, by 1906, the second attempt of restoration of the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba was much advanced and the paved platform on which the *dāgāba* stands had been unearthed. The Archaeological Department tried to repair the Stūpa by mantling the remaining mound with bricks, but this work was abandoned by them later due to lack of funds, when the height of the new dome stood at 60 feet (**Plate 6**). All four Vahālkāḍas, also known as frontispieces, described H. C. P. Bell as Mandapaya and formerly partly hidden under tons of debris, were freed by 1906. The North Mandapaya, excavated in 1903, was described as being in a perfect condition. The East Mandapaya had little damage, the South Mandapaya was in a wonderful state of preservation, and the West Mandapaya (**Plates 3–4**) as perfect as the North Mandapaya.⁴ Today only one Vahālkāḍa survives more or less intact (**Plates 28–30**). According to A. M. Hocart, in 1928 all four cardinal points of the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba *vahālkāḍa* structures were built of gneiss. It has been proposed that these represent later copies of the damaged dolomite marble originals.⁵ At present, after the fourth restoration, the last two times by the Archaeological Department of Sri Lanka under the supervision of Roland Silva, only the West Vahālkāḍa remains intact. However, it had to be restored after having been destroyed when the renovated *dāgāba* collapsed on the 24th of June 1987 (**Plates 27–29**). Of the other three Vahālkāḍas that were in a perfect condition one hundred years ago, only damaged remains of one of the three others survive (**Plate 30**). During the 20th century various renovation works of the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba were carried out, although some without detailed written records. An anonymous photograph documents restoration works in the 1920s. It likely appears to document the second attempt by the Archaeological Department of Sri Lanka to encase the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba with bricks (**Plate 5**).

³ Bell, H. C. P. 1890. *Second Report on the Archaeological Survey of Anuradhapura*: 1, Area E.

⁴ Bell, H. C. P. 1906. *Archaeological Survey of Ceylon. North-Central and Central Provinces. Annual Report. 1906*: 2–8, pls. I–VIII.

⁵ Hocart, A. M. 1928. *Ceylon Journal of Science (Section G)*, Vol. II, Part 1: 6.

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3. Vahālkāḍa structures built of gneiss facing west. Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at in the 1880s. (Photo: Skeen & Co 1880–1890s, albumen print).

4. Vahālkāḍa structures built of gneiss facing west. Mirisavetiya Dāgāba in 1895. (Photo: Archaeological Department of Sri Lanka).

From 1980 onward, a third attempt was undertaken to renovate the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba. It was done by the efforts of a Stūpa Development Society with the help of the Department of Archaeology under the supervision of Roland Silva (1933–2020), Archaeological Commissioner and Director-General, Cultural Triangle (**Plates 7–10**). The restoration attempt ended with the sudden collapse of the newly renovated Mirisavetiya Dāgāba on 24th of June 1987, the day before the Poson Poya Day. The collapse, that also destroyed the only surviving Vahālkāḍa, occurred immediately as the chanting started in the all night Pirith Ceremony, triggering theories of a "curse of the gods". (**Plates 13–15**). Large segments of the new brick-work of the Stūpa separated and fell off due to the several vertical cracks that already earlier had been noticed on the dome (**Plates 11–12**). This happened in the presence of the assembly of monks presided over by Sirimalwatte Sri Ananda Thero (1973–1989). Among the distinguished guests present were President Ranasinghe Premadasa, ministers, ambassadors as well as the whole press corps and countless onlookers. The wide media exposure led to a public outcry and was a big embarrassment for the government as well as the Archaeological Department and the UNESCO Cultural Triangle project. This calamity prevented the planned pinnacle unveiling ceremony and enshrinement of relics on the Poson Poya Day. Instead, the collapsed *dāgāba* had to be demolished. This was achieved by using pneumatic hammers and took almost three years to be accomplished (**Plates 16–19**). After the low-quality bricks of the third attempted restoration had been removed, only the weak inner core of the original Stūpa survived (**Plate 20**). In 1990, the reconstruction of a new *dāgāba* with bricks and layers of reinforced cement began at the spot where the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba used to be, again supervised by Roland Silva, the Archaeological Commissioner (**Plates 21–24**). The new *dāgāba*, that represented the fourth attempt of restoration, was ceremonially unveiled on 4th of June 1993, the Poson full moon day. Although the archaeologists had wished not to plaster the newly built Stūpa, it was nevertheless done at the request of the Buddhist council. The covering of the newly built *dāgāba* with white plaster was finished in 1996. The present monument that encloses the remnants of the original *dāgāba* has lost all characteristics of the original edifice. The present Mirisavetiya Dāgāba is 192 feet (59 metres) in height and 141 feet (43 metres) in diameter (**Plates 25–26**).

Select References to the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba

- Smither, James G. 1894. *Architectural Remains, Anurādhapura, Ceylon*: 19–22, pls. XIV–XXI.
- Harris, G. 1900. *Report on the Restoration of the Abhayagiri and Mirisavetiya Dagaba*: 4 plans.
- Paranavitana, Senarat. 1946. *The Stūpa in Ceylon. Memoirs of the Archaeological Survey of Ceylon*, Vol. V: 6, 17, 35, 47, 50 ff., 58, 61 f., pls. II (a), VI (b), VIII, X [b].
- Weeraratne, Edith. 1970. "The Mirisaveti Vihare of Anuradhapura". In: *Buddhist Yearly 1968–69*. Jahrbuch für Buddhistische Forschungen: 28–49.
- Silva, Roland. 1990. "The engineering principles behind the largest brick monuments of the ancient world: the colossal stupas of Sri Lanka." In: *Perspectives in Archaeology: Leelananda Prematilleke Festschrift 1990*. (Department of Archaeology. University of Peradeniya): 111–119.
- von Schroeder, Ulrich. 1990. *Buddhist Sculptures of Sri Lanka*: 350, 595, fig. A75.
- Silva, W.N.G. 2007. *Conservation of Ancient Dagobas in Sri Lanka*. Engineer: Journal of the Institution of Engineers, Sri Lanka, 40 (3).

5. Renovations of the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura in 1920. It appears to document likely the second attempt by the Archaeological Department of Sri Lanka to encase the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba with bricks. (Albumen print by unknown photographer. Ulrich von Schroeder Collection).

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6. Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura as it looked before the second attempt of restoration in 1980. The Archaeological Department had tried earlier to repair the Stūpa by mantling the remaining mound with bricks, but this work was abandoned by them later when the height of the new dome stood at 60 feet. (Albumen print by unknown photographer).

7. The Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura during reconstruction works in May 1985. The third attempt of renovation was under the supervision of Roland Silva (1933–2020), Archaeological Commissioner and Director-General of the Cultural Triangle. (Photo: Cyril Basnayake).

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8. The third attempt of renovation of the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba in May 1986. (Photo: Cyril Basnayake).

9. The third attempt of renovation of the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba in June 1987. (Photo: Cyril Basnayake).

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10. The third attempt of renovation of the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura in June 1987, a few days before the Poson Poya Day on 25th of June 1987. (Photo: Cyril Basnayake).

11. Cracks at the newly restored Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura early June 1987, few days before the planned enshrinement of relics. (Photo: Cyril Basnayake).

12. Large segments of the newly restored Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura collapse on the 24th of June 1987. This happened immediately as the chanting started in the all night Pirith Ceremony. (Photo: Cyril Basnayake).

13. Large segments of the newly restored Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura collapse on 24th of June 1987 during the Pirith Ceremony the day before the Poson Poya Day. (Photo: Cyril Basnayake).

14. Large segments of the newly restored Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura collapse on the 24th of June 1987 as the chanting started in the all night Pirith Ceremony. (Photo: Cyril Basnayake).

15. Large segments of the newly restored Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura collapse on the 24th of June 1987 in front of a great crowd of spectators. (Photo: Cyril Basnayake).

16. Demolishing of the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura in 1988, one year after the collapse hours prior to the enshrinement of relics. (Photo: Cyril Basnayake).

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17. Demolishing of the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura in 1988, using pneumatic hammers. (Photo: Cyril Basnayake).

18. Demolishing of the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura in 1988. One year after the collapse of the ill-fated third attempt of restoration. (Photo: Cyril Basnayake).

19. Demolishing of the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura in November 1989. Two years after the collapse of the ill-fated third attempt of restoration. (Photo: Ulrich von Schroeder).

20. Demolishing of the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura in 1990, three years after the collapse. Only the weak inner core of the original Stūpa does survive. (Photo: Cyril Basnayake).

21. Scaffoldings erected by the Archaeological Department of Sri Lanka during the second attempt to restore the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba as in January 1992. (Photo: Ulrich von Schroeder, 1992).

22. The second attempt by the Archaeological Department to restore the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba in January 1992. Workers laying layers of bricks. (Photo: Ulrich von Schroeder, 1992).

23. The second attempt to restore the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba in January 1992. Layers of cement were added to prevent another collapse. (Photo: Ulrich von Schroeder, 1992).

24. The second attempt by the Archaeological Department to restore the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba. The present monument completed in the 1993 that encloses the remnants of the original *dāgāba* has lost all ancient characteristics of the original edifice. (Photo: Ulrich von Schroeder, 1993).

25. The newly constructed Mirisavetiya Dāgāba in 1993. Although the archaeologists had wished not to plaster the newly built *dāgāba*, it was nevertheless done on request of the Buddhist council. (Photo: U. von Schroeder, January 1993).

26. The newly built *dāgāba* in circa 2020 at the spot where the Mirisavetiya Dāgāba used to be. The new *dāgāba* is 192 feet (59 metres) in height and 141 feet (43 metres) in diameter. (Photo: Vigi Senarath).

27. Reconstruction of the western Vahālkaḍa structures of the newly built Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura during the third attempt of restoration. (Photo: Ulrich von Schroeder, January 1993).

28. Western Vahāḷkaḍa structures of the newly built Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura in 2015.
(Photo D.C. Ranatunga).

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29. Remains of Vahālkaḍa structure of the newly built Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura in 2017.
(Photo: Explore Sri Lanka).

30. Remains of Vahālkaḍa structure of the newly built Mirisavetiya Dāgāba at Anurādhapura in 2017.
(Photo: Explore Sri Lanka).